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Data Management Plan (DMP I)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project background

In COEVOLVERS DMP will be developed outlining procedures of data management (incl. existing data, original research data, compilation of databases, models, etc.), archiving and accessibility following Horizon Europe guidelines. COEVOLVERS' main aim is to foster societal benefits in biodiversity and climate crisis management through advancing coevolutionary theory and nature-based solutions (NBS) that encourage regenerative social processes. By uniting diverse stakeholders in seven European Living Labs (LL), the project seeks to collaboratively create fair NBS governance approaches, models, and tools. Small-Scale Pilots will also be conducted with other EU projects and Cousins in the Americas. Ultimately, COEVOLVERS strives to transform local governance by aligning with the European Green Deal (EGD), Agenda 2030 Biodiversity and Climate Adaptation Strategies, and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). COEVOLVERS are determined in implementing a transformative change to meet ambitious targets to achieve the EU climate adaptation and biodiversity strategies, it becomes essential to address effectively how to connect NBS and everyday life practices and non-human modes of life.

Luke, as the responsible partner for the implementation of the DMP (D 7.1), will coordinate with all WP leaders and Living Lab core group members to ensure compliance. The DMP content will be disseminated among all LL team members to align their LL actions with the DMP. Continuous feedback from Living Labs will be used to update the DMP as needed. Luke will communicate with all WP leaders and LL core team members, gathering the necessary information to update the DMP.

1.2. Data Management Plan (DMP) and FAIR principles

An effective data management plan and practice is pivotal for the development of NBS related data and knowledge base aiming to address the challenges related to data heterogeneity, quality control, data flexibility and integration, reproducibility and

extensibility, data acceptability and collaboration, and guidance for future research and implementation of NBS initiatives ([Dushkova and Hasse, 2020](#)) In line with data management requirements set out in EC Horizon 2020 Online Manual, in COEVOLVERS we implement the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) principles, open access to publications, open access to data, and Data Management Plan to ensure effective data collection and integration, data accessibility and sharing, data privacy and security, data quality and reliability, data analysis and interpretation, data visualisation and communication, data storage and archiving, future data usage for capacity building and training, monitoring and evaluating and interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. Open access to data refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable, which may include peer-reviewed scientific research articles or research data is raw or curated.

1.3. GDPR, personal data privacy and protection

GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679 - General Data Protection Regulation) lays down rules for the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and the free movement of personal data and protects fundamental rights to the protection of personal data and ensures that the personal data should flow freely within the European Union without restrictions for individuals protection reasons ([GDPR, 2016](#)). DGPR also aims to empower citizens in decision-making regarding the use of their personal data.

According to European Commission (EC), GDPR defines personal data as to any information related to an identifiable living person, including different pieces of information that, when combined, can identify someone. De-identified, encrypted, or pseudonymized data that can be used to re-identify a person is also considered personal data under GDPR. Data that has been irreversibly anonymized, making the individual unidentifiable, is not considered personal data. GDPR safeguards personal data regardless of processing technology or storage method, whether it's automated or manual, in an IT system, through video surveillance, or on paper.

1.4. Knowledge Platform and DMP

A digital platform will be used to benefit the data storage and data sharing in between relevant parties involved in the project and the overall data management in the project. A digital platform can enhance the storage of data for the purpose of research verification, enabling access, editing, reuse, and post-project data utilisation. The incorporation of a secure digital platform can mitigate the potential risks of data loss and misuse.

Figure 1. Digital and data ecosystem in COEVOLVERS show a complexity of data management requirements, and therefore necessitates a carefully structured data management plan (DMP) to guide all parties involved in the project including researchers, the living lab (LL) core group, stakeholders, decision-makers and the local community.

Citizen science in COEVOLVERS is anticipated to produce socio-cultural data pertinent to the impact of NBS and socio-environmental equity and justice. The digital platform will be responsible for safeguarding and storing that data gathered through apps such as PPGIS. In establishing the digital platform, adherence to legal

regulations, anonymisation, secure data storage, restricted access, and compliance with the TISAX rule set will be ensured.

COEVOLVERS will guarantee data rights, including the right to erasure, data portability, and protection from automated decisions, although these rights may be limited or subject to exemptions. The project will ensure that any concerns regarding data management using the digital platform can be addressed to the coordinator, complaints can be filed with the supervisory authority, and any changes to the privacy policy will be published on the project website.

1.5. Structure of the document

The following section will focus on the data types and format, FAIR principles, research outputs for example publications and metadata, resource allocation and development of digital platform, data security and long-term data preservation and curation and basic ethics principles that entails DMP.

2. Data Summary

The objective of the DMP is to ensure that research data and corresponding metadata are discoverable, accessible, assessable, reusable, and exchangeable in the context of COEVOLVERS's living labs (LL). The research data may consist of various information types, such as personal information (including vulnerable groups participating in LL activities), facts about community benefits related to NBS implementation, existing socio-political conflicts concerning NBS usage and environmental justice, socio-demographic data, spatial data, observations, photographs, interviews, and workshop recordings. These data will be employed for analysis and reasoning within the research context. The DMP will also concentrate on digital data products and contents, as well as publications, articles, lectures, presentations, tools, software, and project deliverables etc. COEVOLVER will gather raw data, process it, and summarize it in deliverables, publications, policy briefs, video stories, and other DEC material. The primary research data sets will be made publicly

available when ensuring the protection of personal data, and post-processing scripts will be openly available and shared. When personal data or data privacy concerns arise, data will be anonymized for publications and other DEC activities.

2.1. General framework for data collection in COEVOLVERS

COEVOLVERS will generate data through various methods applied across different Living Labs, each addressing specific local issues and actions, as well as through different methods and tools, either developed and applied locally or collectively. For details see Table 1. The data types can be broadly classified into two categories: 1) Primary data, e.g., data collected through tasks in LLs and WPs included in WP 3, 4, and 5, such as T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4, T4.1, T5.1, 5.2) Part of WP1, e.g., institutional knowledge, stakeholder information, and baseline information that is pertinent to LLs and both core and supporting groups.

2.1.1. WP1- Living labs for transformative NBS design and implementation.

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will aim to get living labs going by supporting LLs for establishing their core groups, involving key stakeholders, co-create NBS co-creation common principles, support LLs in running co-creation activities and core groups for using different digital tools and, art-based methods, and bespoke methods, and organise training and coordination for data collection. Within WP1, the focus will be to assess learning within and across living labs and Overseas Cousins (Ocs), which includes base line study of researchers, stakeholders, and participants, conduct mobility programme, to learn across LLs, and synthesise results. WP 1 will support with the development and application of digital and art-based tools and methods, organise trainings and assess their user experience (T 1.2, T 1.3). To achieve this goal, WP1 in COEVOLVERS will collect following data:

- Literature repository i.e. T 1.2 (responsible partner Luke, supported by ESSRG, HUTT, IFE SAS, and all LLs), and T 1.4 (responsible partner ESSRG, supported by Luke, HUTT, IFE SAS, all LLs)- to support the review of current

state-of-the-art of digital tools, art-based methods, co-creation methodologies, collaborative digital platforms for knowledge sharing.

- Develop, plan, implement digital tools and methods, and assess of user experience (T1.2 and T 1.3) - to collect place-based non-human umwelt using stories and narratives and information in social use of NBS and human-nonhuman interactions related to NBS(s) or NBS-related themes and issues that are in question.
- Implement assessment of learning using "systematisation of experience" - to collect personal and collective reflections on the co-creation activities to induce learning towards more transformative NBS design and implementation (T1.4).

2.1.2. WP2- Coevolutionary approach to NBS co-creation

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will theorize and conceptualize NBS as a "coevolutionary technology" to develop principles of co-creation in cooperation with other WPs. The application of coevolutionary approaches will be carried out through workshops, where WP2 will interact with LLs to address their respective NBS challenges. This will result in reports on tools for NBS design and implementation (D 2.3).

2.1.3. WP3- Values and affordances in NBS design and implementation

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will work with stakeholders to find common ground, exploring NBS through shared everyday experiences, feelings, and knowledge associated with specific places and situations. The WP will identify human and non-human affordances, meanings, and significances in LL environments and will produce georeferenced and visualized experiences of these affordances (T 3.2). This will involve onsite active interviews using digital tools, citizen science apps, and GIS-based mapping of affordances. Mapping of vulnerability (T 3.3) will be carried out using storytelling, interviews, and focus group discussions. Stories collected regarding non-human experiences and connections will include some degree of personal data (e.g., name, age, location) and will be collected in compliance with GDPR. In some cases (e.g., Tartu LL), the data will be archived in the Estonian Folklore Archives in

accordance with the ethical guidelines for the Living Labs set within COEVOLVERS (deliverable D1.1 - Ethical guidelines for the Living Labs); otherwise, the data will be anonymized and stored in a secured database in Europe. A pan-EU social survey (T 3.4) will be conducted to measure attitudes, beliefs, and motivations with respect to nature values, NBS, and socio-politics about NBS. The data will be anonymized and stored in a GDPR-compliant database in Europe. Sharing of the data between LLs will follow the Joint Data Agreement (JTA) which is under process, within COEVOLVERS.

2.1.4. WP4- Governance for NBS

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will design, test, and evaluate NBS governance for just digital, economic, and ecological transitions, ensuring the long-term sustainability of urban, rural, coastal, and other EU regions. The WP will assess socio-political aspects of NBS implementation, collecting primary data through semi-structured interviews using a qualitative interview protocol and open online surveys targeting practitioners, users, and implementers of NBS (T4.1, led by IFE SAS). Any personal data will be anonymized and stored in a GDPR-compliant database in Europe.

2.1.5. WP5- Actionable knowledge for transformative NBS

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will synthesize findings from all LLs to co-produce concrete, actionable guidelines for more inclusive NBS. The WP includes tasks that will consult the National Assessment Panel (workshops will be conducted by LL as the primary data collector and later synthesized by Luke (T5.1)), integrating findings into actionable knowledge (led by HUTT (T5.2)). Both tasks will use secondary data, which will be anonymized and stored in a GDPR-compliant database in Europe.

2.1.6. WP6- Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC)

In this WP, COEVOLVERS will continue to develop strategies and plans for DEC, implement communication tools, carry out outreach and exploitation activities, as well as conduct monitoring, assess, and report DEC activities (the WP is led by ESSRG).

The data gathered or synthesized in this WP will be stored in a GDPR-compliant database in Europe.

2.1.7. WP7- Project coordination and administration

In WP, COEVOLVERS will oversee project coordination and administrative tasks. This document (D7.1/T7.3) ensures that the data produced, acquired, synthesized, published, exploited, and disseminated, along with the procedures including data management (e.g., existing data, original research data, compilation of databases, and models), archiving, and accessibility, comply with Horizon Europe guidelines. During project management activities, while being involved in various research activities across LLS, and synthesizing data as described in certain tasks, Luke (as WP lead) will handle both primary and secondary data (which is anonymized) and will store the data in a secure, GDPR-compliant database in Europe.

2.2. Data description

The COEVOLVERS project acknowledges the importance of the open science practices and knowledge co-creation in fostering widest adaptation of NBS in Europe which will be achieved through participatory implementation. COEVOLVERS will follow the principles of open science as fully as possible, via cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible, in accordance with the ethical principles of research, the publishers' terms and conditions, and legislation (incl. Finland's National Declaration for Open Science & Research, 2020–2025, to which Luke is a signatory). In addition, external stakeholders will be encouraged to participate in co-creation activities i.e. data collection, research and solutions. When required, GDPR compliance and intellectual property (IP) protection may delay or limit open access to research outcome.

The project's open science practices will include:

- As early as possible and open sharing of research.
- Research output management according to FAIR principles.

- Measures to ensure replicability and upscaling of research results and tools.
- Open access (OA) to research outputs (publications, datasets)
- Involving relevant stakeholders and local communities and non-humans (in knowledge co-creation pertaining to NBS).

COEVOLVERS will establish a Zenodo community as a reliable international archive, for collecting and sharing research outputs and open access data alongside repositories maintained by the participant organisations. Prior to depositing, the personal data will be processed so that no individual can be reasonably identified based on the provided data or through combining the data with additional data sources. Direct and indirect identification of research outputs will be made impossible. In addition, COEVOLVERS will adhere to the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) in managing research data and other research outputs.

The four FAIR principles can be applied in different ways: Data will be stored in repositories (A). Data will be described and published using research metadata (FAI). Data will be assigned a digital object identifier (doi) (FAIR). The OA data will be discoverable, accessible, and downloadable (FAIR). The entire data management process will be documented and verified (data collection methods, editing, software used, analysis, codes, variables, standards), facilitating the reproduction of research using the same datasets and methods (IR). Metadata will be maintained and enriched accordingly throughout the research process (IR). Data will be open after the publication of respective results (A).

The following Creative Commons licences will be used: CC BY 4.0 for open data that allow others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the data, even commercially, as long as they credit the original creator; CC0 (no rights reserved) for metadata – allows others to freely build upon, enhance and reuse the data for any purpose, without restriction under copyright or database law.

2.3. Re-use of any existing data

COEVOLVERS will refrain from utilising any existing or previously gathered personal data (e.g., membership lists). The primary source of the data will mainly be the participants from seven Living Labs (LL) who will be identified and selected during the project. A survey for the stakeholders in the regions of the LLs will be carried out during the second year of the project. The respondents will be identified using information obtained from the interviews conducted in the LLs. Nevertheless, COEVOLVERS will utilise publicly accessible spatial, environmental, and socio-economic data from the LL region.

2.4. Types and formats of data

Data will be collected from the LLs using online and in-situ surveys, co-creation workshops, personal interviews, observations, art-based methods, GIS etc. The data collected will be stored in .xlsx, .csv, .docx, .MOV or .jpg formats. Interviews will be stored as the original audio file (.wmf or similar), a text file (.rtf or similar) containing its transcription in the original language, and a text file containing its translation into English.

Each partner that collects personal data will be responsible for storing and maintaining them at his/her institution in accordance with GDPR. Data containing the names, addresses or other personal contact details will be stored in files separately to data on their responses to surveys, interviews workshops etc. Such data will be pseudonymised: Data will be stored, by each LL partner, as separate folders for different file categories (transcripts, tables, pictures, etc.).

2.5. Description of data and metadata

Each dataset collected, processed, or generated within the project will include a brief descriptive table, followed by a detailed information sheet for every dataset.

Table 1. Content of the dataset.

Data Set Information	Details
Name	Complete title of the data set

Description	- Purpose of data collection
	- Origin of data
	- Dataset contents
	- Added value
	- Collection method (if relevant)
	- Use in scientific publication (if yes, include content and journal)
Media Type	Type of content medium (e.g., video, image, text, numerical data)
Language(s)	Language(s) of the dataset content
Publication Date	Date the data set was published or uploaded
Use & Re-Use Conditions	- Potential users
	- Barriers for re-use
	- Embargo period (if applicable)
Size	Size of the resource (specify unit)
Format & License	Data format (e.g., .xls, .csv, .txt) and licensing information
Version Number	Version number of the data set
Persistent Identifier	DOI or other identifier (e.g., 10.1000/xyz123)
Project Info	"COEVOLVERS, funded by EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant No. 101084220"

Table 2. Data summary

	New/existing data	Purpose	Type	Format	Size	Data storage during the project	Data storage after the project	Personal data (Y/N)	Anonymisation (Y/N)/Pseudonymisation (Y/N)	Owner of the original data	Re-usability (Y/N)	For whom data could be useful?	Contact person
WP1 - Living labs for transformative NBS design and implementation													
T1.1. Getting Living Labs going	New	The list of core group participants	list	.doc	<1 M	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Y	N, N	Each LL	no		Each LL/Katriina Soini (WP1 leader)
T1.1. Getting Living Labs going	New	Consent forms	signed forms	.doc	<1 M	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Y	N, N	Each LL	no		Each LL/Katriina Soini (WP1 leader)
T1.1. Getting Living Labs going	New	Ethical workshop co-creation materials	short reports with images, recordings	.mp3, .jpg,	<5 M	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	N	N, N	Each LL	no		Each LL/Katriina Soini (WP1 leader)
T1.2. Providing and assessing the working tools		Literature review on methodologies	descriptions	.doc				N					

T1.2. Providing and assessing the working tools			training material										
T1.3. Running co-creation activities		workshops	guidelines, meeting notes	.doc									
T1.4. Learning within and across LLs		Developing a protocol to assesing learning,	qualitative data on collaboration and learning at the LL and stakeholder group level				N						
T1.4 Mobility programme		Mobility plan	Document	.doc									
WP2 Coevolutionary approach to NBS co-creation													
Theory and concepts	Research data		manuscripts	.doc	<1 M		N						
WP3 Values and affordances in NBS design and implementation													
T3.1. Searching for common ground	New	To explore the NBS sites together with the participatns of LLs	recordings, photos, videos, drawings, texts	.mp3, .jpg,		A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Y	Y, Y	Each of the LL	no	?	Each LL leader and the Task leader (Luke)

T3.2. Mapping the affordances	New	Interview recordings, data on non-human participants, affordances, and umwelts	recordings, notes, tables	.wav, .xdoc, .xlsx	<1Gb	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Y	Y, Y	UT	yes		Timo Maran
T3.3. Understanding the vulnerabilities	New	Storytelling, focus groups, interviews	recorded audio	.wmf, mp3, .jpg,				Y					
T.3.3 Understanding the vulnerabilities	New	Social media	qualitative information, notes	.doc				N					
T3.4. Measuring attitudes, beliefs and motivation	New	To measure attitudes, beliefs, motivations in respect to nature values, NBS and the socio-politics about them, including the issue of vulnerability	Questionnaire to be uploaded to an online platform (e.g., Qualtrics)	.xlsx	<1M	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Y	Y, Y	?	Y	?	UNICA Ferdinando Fornara
T3.4.		To compare results with European level surveys and barometers related to environmental attitudes and values, wellbeing indicators, social inclusion level, etc.	text					N					

WP4 - Governance for NBS													
T4.1. Assessment of the socio-politics in NBS implementation	New	Interview guide, interviews, On-line survey with T3.4	text transcripts of interviews	.mp3, .jpg,	<10 M	A joint internal	A joint internal	Y	Y, Y	Slovak Globe - IFE SAS, CETIP, LL conducted interviews	yes	?	WP4 Kluvankova
T4.2. (Re)configuration of institutional scaffolding	New	RBG - Role Board Game	game	text/code	<1Gb	TBC	Research Organisation own archive	Y	Y, Y	Slovak Globe - IFE SAS, CETIP, LL played RBG	no	?	WP4 Kluvankova
T4.3. Co-development of novel NBS governance models	New	RBG - Role Board Game	game	text/code	<1Gb	TBC	Research Organisation own archive	Y	Y, Y	Slovak Globe - IFE SAS, CETIP, LL played RBG	no	?	WP4 Kluvankova
T4.4. Evaluation of NBS governance models, techniques, and tools	New												
WP5 - Actionable knowledge for transformative NBS													

T5.1. Consulting National Assessment Panels	New	To engage national level experts and explore their expectations and needs	recordings, notes, photos	.doc, .jpg, .mp4, .mov, .pm3	<1GB	A joint internal knowledge platform (TBC)	Respective National archive?	Y	Y, Y	Each LL	no	Policy makers, NBS implementers etc.	Each LL
T5.2. Integrating findings for actionable knowledge	Research data	templates for collecting material, used to synthesise findings already collected in other WPs	text	.doc	<20 MB	knowledge platform	platform	N	Y, Y	Each LL	?	NBS implementers, policy makers etc.	Each LL, HUTT
T5.3. Co-designing toolkit	New	workshops	notes, post-its, mindmaps, recordings, videos	.mp3, .jpg,		knowledge platform	platform	Y	Y, Y	Each LL	Yes	Policy makers, NBS implementers etc.	Each LL, HUTT
T5.4. Upscaling and validating the tools	Research data	Validation workshops, interviews	text, photos, recordings	.mp3, .jpg,	<1GB	knowledge platform	platform	Y	Y, Y	WP leader	Yes	Policy makers, NBS implementers etc.	Each LL, HUTT
T5.5. coevolution	old/new	qualitative and quantitative, reusing existing data and survey	recordings, photos, text	.doc, .mp3, .jpg	<1GB	knowledge platform	platform	Y	Y, Y	Each LL	No	All stakeholders	Each LL, CTFC
WP6. Dissemination & Exploitation & Communication													

DEC	Existing	Formulating the chapter on responsible communication in the DEC Strategy	template (spreadsheet)	.doc	<1 M	ESSRG's internal platform	ESSRG's internal platform	Y	Y	Each LL	no	for each partner communicating about the LLs	Éva Bánsági, Mariann Kovács
WP7-Management													
Project coord. & admin.	n	consortium, GA, SC, AB, internal workshops	lists, memos, notes	.doc, .xls	< 1M	Teams	Teams	Y	n	n	n		Luke
WP8 - Ethics Requirements													
Ethical reports 1-4	n	reporting	text	.doc	< 1M	Teams	Teams	n	n	n	n	n	Luke

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The purpose of the data generation

COEVOLVERS aims to enhance the understanding of how NBS are integrated into local culture, practice, and values when implemented locally through the interaction of diverse societal actors in co-creation processes. Additionally, the project seeks to comprehend the establishment of fairer NBS in different contexts. Most of the data will be qualitative by nature, making it more difficult to re-use however, some data could still be used in developing other NBSs nonetheless methodological approach is meant to be replicable across similar contexts in the EU and beyond.

The documentation of the LLs will be included of scientific articles and other project reports, news articles etc. to inform decision-making at national or regional or international levels. Various actions of the LLs will be documented through recording or photographs, or video documentation. All collected data such as interview materials and workshop agendas, minutes and notes will be stored on the project's digital platform by the responsible research teams and will be used as research data.

2.6. Data Lifecycle

In COEVOLVERS, we manage the data lifecycle as follows:

- Data is initially collected across various Living Labs (LLs) with support from Work Packages (WPs).
- Data is stored and shared based on its confidentiality and sensitivity. It is kept in LLs and the project's secure (GDPR-compliant) database, i.e., Nextcloud during the project lifetime (Germany, EU) and in Tiimeri after the project ends (Finland, EU).
- Primary data is anonymized and exchanged between LLs and WPs.
- Data is published through deliverables and peer-reviewed journals (following Horizon Europe guidelines) and archived in Zenodo, using an open access license when possible or with restricted access if necessary. It is also stored in the project's intranet system, Nextcloud.

Data collected by Overseas Cousins is processed according to the respective country's laws and best practices (e.g., Carriacou, Grenada; Piura region, Peru). No European LL data is shared outside the EU, and only anonymized data is accepted by EU partners and stored in secure EU databases.

The use and re-use conditions for specific data will be determined by the COEVOLVERS's Steering Committee and included in the metadata of the publishable datasets. Data for project operation, monitoring, and management will not be publicly available for re-use.

Figure 2. Data Lifecycle within COEVOLVERS

2.7. Data Storage in COEVOLVERS

In COEVOLVERS, data is stored in NextCloud (i.e. GDPR-compliant data storage platform <https://nextcloud.coevolvers-digital.eu/index.php/apps/dashboard/#/>) during

the lifetime of the project. LLs will establish their own secure data storage. Access to this knowledge platform is secured through user password (both single and double authentication process), and the activities on the platform is monitored. Post-project the data will be stores in secured platform.

i.e. <https://tila.tiimeri.fi/SitePages/Home.aspx>.

2.8. DPM versions

According to the EU's guidelines on the Data Management Plan (DMP) (European Commission, 2016), the DMP can be updated as needed throughout the project's duration, typically as part of deliverable submissions. The DMP must be updated at least during the project's periodic evaluations, or by the final review if no evaluations occur.

The DMP is designed to be a living document, allowing for more detailed updates as the project implementation advances. Each version of the DMP should be clearly numbered and include a schedule for updates.

3. FAIR data

In the COEVOLVERS project Zenodo will be used for depositing data sets, research software, reports[±], and any other research related digital artifacts. The COEVOLVERS community at Zenodo is available at [here](https://zenodo.org/communities/coevolvers_2022/) (https://zenodo.org/communities/coevolvers_2022/). Any data and/or publications etc. stored in some other trusted repository or services (including any digital platform, Tiimeri etc.) will be linked to the project's Zenodo community for easy overview and access. Data and metadata information will be readily available to global research and non-research communities, ensuring easy findability. Deposition of data will be commenced as soon as possible following data production/generation or once adequate processing and quality control have been completed, adding value and

context to the data and this will be done no later than the end of the project. In exceptional cases in which specific constraints or restrictions are in place (e.g. security rules), data deposition might be delayed beyond the end of the project. Data underpinning a scientific publication will be deposited at the latest at the time of publication, or in accordance with standard community practices.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Datasets in Zenodo will be identified by a DOI. Basic metadata will be generated in Zenodo and in other trusted repositories to enable data discovery as different methods and materials for different work packages (WPs) are determined, finalised, and implemented, additional metadata created in different WPs will be supplemented later. Where necessary, detailed dataset level disciplinary-based metadata will be created. In Zenodo and other trusted repositories, to optimise data findability, discoverability, and reusability, keywords will be provided in the metadata. Metadata will be offered in a way that it can be harvested and indexed.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

Repository

The data will be stored in Zenodo or/and other trusted repositories. Throughout the lifetime of the project, appropriate arrangements with the identified repository will be explored as required. Zenodo provides a DOI for data sets and other digital objects and is also responsible for resolving these DOIs.

Data

We will follow the principles of open science as comprehensibly, early and widely as possible. When necessary, personal data issues and protection of intellectual property (IP) may occasionally delay or limit or restrict data access. GDPR restricts the use of personal data, allowing only anonymous versions can be openly accessible. Further use of the data will be described in the privacy policy, which covers the entire life cycle

of the data including information on when the data is destroyed (retention periods, etc.).

Mata data for both individual records and record collections can be harvested using the OAI-PMH protocol in Zenodo by using the record identifier and collection name. metadata can be retrieved via the public REST API. From Zenodo records, a user (human or machine) can download one or more files. Zenodo metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under the public domain. No authorization will be necessary to retrieve the metadata however, the protocol of Zenodo allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary. The dataset will be accessible upon reasonable request from the corresponding author If there are any restrictions on their use. The steering committee will evaluate data requests as required.

Data Licencing

Data licensing standards specify the terms of data set accessibility. There are numerous license types available; however, this document will not provide a detailed discussion of them. In COEVOLVERS we use common data licensing according to Open Access obligations in Horizon Europe, following https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/open-access-obligations-horizon-europe-what-are-cc-licences-2021-11-15_en.

Metadata

Zenodo metadata is licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. Zenodo metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing. The metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed. Documents stored in Zenodo will be retained for the operational lifetime of the repository. This is the present lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which has an experimental programme defined for at least the next 20 years. Metadata in Zenodo will be accessible, even when the data are no longer available. COEVOLVERS will only use openly accessible and standard data formats e.g., CSV, Excel, ASCII-text, etc.

Making data interoperable

The COEVOLVERS project will generate and develop new ontologies, and vocabularies in addition to the existing vocabularies, standards, formats, and methodologies of social science, humanities, and design thinking. In COEVOLVERS, once we have a more thorough understanding, we will create guidelines regarding their publication and reuse.

Increase data re-use

The objective of the project is to guarantee open access as feasible and widely during and beyond the project's duration, acknowledging the limits of the GDPR and other legislation concerning human participants, and possible protection and/or exploitation of their interests. Later at various stages of the project, data quality assurance processes will be clarified, and they will be included in updated versions of the DMP as required. Data quality and integrity for WPs will be addressed in future planning meetings. In general, the open data will be made available for re-use under CC BY - license and metadata under CC0.

3.3. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data exploitation

This Data Management Plan (DMP) addresses Intellectual Property (IP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) within the COEVOLVERS project, especially keeping in mind the uptake of results produced within the project and during the life cycle of the project. It details the protection, access, and exploitation of IP in line with the Consortium Agreement (Sections: Open Science, Page 22; IPR, Page 30) and the Project Grant Agreement, as outlined in Article 16 and Annex 5. Adherence to the terms set forth in these agreements is required for all IP generated or co-generated within the consortium, ensuring alignment with all project objectives and collaboration protocols.

In this project, intellectual property encompasses any created or produced results, including know-how, materials, methods, procedures, and data. Ownership rights over

such results are defined by the organisation responsible for their generation. However, co-generated results—where knowledge contributions are inseparable among partners—will follow co-ownership rules based on consortium agreements, fostering fair and equitable use of collective project outcomes. With regards to co-ownership, by considering different interest and objectives of involved partners, we ensure issues related data or result management, dissemination, protection, transfer/licencing and exploitation in advance are addressed and subsequent changes in time as necessary are made (Horizon Europe, 2022- The European IP Helpdesk. The IP Framework: IP related Rules and Requirements). An IP strategy for COEVOLVERS aims to ensure effective management, protection, and exploitation of intellectual property throughout the project lifecycle, in line with Horizon Europe guidelines.

Principles of data generation, ownership, and sharing

This DMP establishes principles and internal guidelines to ensure responsible data generation, management, and curation practices. Ownership rights apply to both pre-existing and newly generated data. Existing data utilised in project activities will retain its original ownership, with usage rights extended to consortium partners under the agreed conditions. New data created collaboratively will be managed through co-ownership agreements, promoting shared access while safeguarding individual contributions.

The COEVOLVERS project's IP strategy takes key steps and considerations at each phase: at the start of the project, during project implementation, and after project completion. During project implementation we will consider the use of existing and potential knowledge creation and at the partner and consortium level will discuss different possible IP protection methods and identify potential complementary IP protection methods. Regarding the data exploitation after the project ends, at the consortium level, we will discuss and agree on joint exploitation of results and knowledge co-created and look at possible IP ownership arrangement and related responsibilities and licencing agreements.

To ensure fair application, COEVOLVERS ensure data access rights are based on roles and project needs. Partners who generate commercially exploitable IP retain ownership rights but are encouraged to collaborate with other partners and discuss these matters at the Steering Committee (SC) meetings and the General Assembly (GA) (GA) to maximise impact, enhancing data usability for consortium members or potential external stakeholders. For example, a dataset owned by Partner A may be shared with Partner B for specific project purposes, with usage limitations clarified under an agreement within the consortium framework.

IPR methodology

In COEVOLVERS IPR methodology is built on the strategy as mentioned focus on key questions:

1. What knowledge is co-creation and results are or will be produced?
2. Who owns and co-own the result and the knowledge? (here the focus is about the ownership types and co-sharing of ownership using an exploitation strategy for results)
3. What risks can be seen for exploitation of results?
4. Who are the beneficiaries (or impact groups) of the results and knowledge developed in COEVOLVERS? (i.e. identification impact target groups or beneficiaries)
5. What are the ways to exploit the knowledge and strategies to protect different results?

Responsibilities and exploitation of project results

Responsibilities for identifying, managing, and exploiting project results lie with Work Package (WP) leaders, tasked with early identification of innovative results and initiating discussions for their development and commercial application. Joint innovation management is a standing item at SC and GA meetings, with key outputs and advancements regularly incorporated into and updated in the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) plan (D 6.2.). The DEC plan is updated

continuously to reflect project progress and align with emerging opportunities for data and IP exploitation.

To ensure coherence, any decisions related to data ownership, usage, or planned exploitation must be discussed within the SC as the main discussion forum. The GA remains the primary decision-making platform, where partners can confirm agreed actions and review data handling policies. This approach fosters transparent collaboration and pre-planning, enabling all parties to contribute meaningfully to the project outcomes. The exploitation of results will be considered as means for commercially and non-commercially exploitable.

At the project partner and over all consortium, out IP strategy is to discuss:

1. The individual and joint contribution and rights to the input of IP (as Background IP) at the start of the project, and during the project (as Foreground IP).
2. Clearly define exploitation goals and risk by identifying key beneficiaries of NBS development and governance. They may include:
 - Citizens and civil society
 - Cities and municipalities
 - Policymakers
 - Living lab core-group and the members of the community
 - National Consultation Groups
 - Stakeholders
 - Academia and Research Universities
 - Scientists
 - Urbanists, engineers, landscape architects, urban planners, ecologists etc.
 - Forestry and natural resources institutes
 - Forest, urban forest, urban landscape managers, shepherds, farmers etc.

- COEVOLVERS overseas cousins and third parties (NetworkNature, and HE projects)
- Institutional organisations and city governments
- Environmental NGOs

Access rights and external data sharing

Data sharing is structured around principles of accessibility and fairness. Data citation is an essential factor in promoting data access, sharing, and reuse. Data users should apply a consistent citation style to data sets, similar to how they cite literature in their publications. The main citation elements are the author(s), title, date, publisher (the unique identifier of the repository or archive hosting the data), version number, and access information (e.g., DOI or URN). When cited data belongs to a specific repository, the repository may provide recommended citation guidelines or even a ready-made citation for the retrieved data. Each COEVOLVERS output will include information of the project and the funding: “The data/other output were produced by the COEVOLVERS project, funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No. 101084220.”

For external access to data, users must contact the COEVOLVERS Consortium with an intended usage outline. This process requires a data-sharing agreement, co-signed by the user and an authorised institutional official, before access is granted. This requirement is also reflected in project metadata, ensuring transparency and traceability. However, in case of open data provision under CC license, users don’t need to undergo any data-sharing agreement.

Practical scenarios illustrating data ownership and use

To clarify data use cases, the DMP includes practical examples of data generation, management, and ownership, for example:

1. Reuse of existing data

Partner A provides an environmental dataset that supports COEVOLVEVRS project goals. New insights derived from this data benefit the consortium, with rights to the newly generated data shared among contributors to the task.

2. Method and tool development and contextualisation

A partner develops a method, such as a role board game or a Citizen Science App, which other partners contextualise within varied settings i.e. in their respective living labs contexts. This collaborative refinement process results in co-owned IP, recognising each partner's input.

3. Collaborative data co-creation

Multiple partners collect data part of a task including for example, participating in method development workshops, contributing to the development of the method i.e. a survey, translating the survey into local language, administering the survey in the local context, each offering distinct contextual insights. The final dataset is co-owned and shared for project use, with potential for external access governed by DEC and consortium guidelines.

COEVOLVEVRS IPR management model

By establishing a structured, equitable approach to data ownership and access, the COEVOLVEVRS ensures all consortium partners have a clear understanding of their rights and responsibilities, enabling effective collaboration and maximising the project's impact. COEVOLVEVRS IPR model includes the following strands:

- COEVOLVEVRS partners generates knowledge, that is 1) open access, 2) closed data (if necessary to do so)
- COEVOLVEVRS generate knowledge with extrarenal parties i.e. local entity or community in respective living labs which use co-creation and learning modules.

- COEVOLVERS define IPRs for tools and methods developed and co-developed within the project.
- COEVEOLEVRS define wide dissemination and exploitation (D&E) plan for all IPs and ownership and co-ownership of IPs.
- COEVEOLEVRS develop thematic and Impact guidelines that exploit results.
- Use of IP in COEVOLEVRS business models.

4.1. Other research outputs

COEVOLVERS will generate additional research outputs than publications and data. Among other outputs *Role Board Game (RBG)* and *Virtual Nature* digital tools, are further developed in the project. RBG will be incorporated into the NBS governance reconfiguration deliberation process. It will be modelled further for the various LL conditions and contexts. Virtual Nature tool is a web-based software/app. An addition for this project is the development of an app to allow viewers to add images to the virtual experience. Another project outputs will be the development of an online participatory mapping tool to capture place-specific human and non-human interactions and experiences related to NBS. In addition, the project also will design different protocols e.g., a protocol to reflect learning in collaborative activities and an evaluation framework for assessing NBS governance models, techniques, and tools.

At the later stage in the project, the management, sharing and re-using of other research output in line with the FAIR data principles will be clarified. The information will be included in the updated versions of the DMP.

4.2. Allocation of resources

Luke is responsible for coordinating the overall data management. The lead contact at each participating organisation will be responsible for coordinating the data management in the organisation in question including the collection and transfer of

data from its own research activities, within the framework of the DMP. The coordinator and the lead contacts at participant organisations will collaborate with involved data and other experts when needed. The coordinator is responsible for that research outputs are in line with the FAIR data principles, and that every consortium partner has also committed to the FAIR principles. The costs will be covered during the project by the Horizon Europe grant during the duration of the project and by partner institutions after the project's conclusion. The costs associated with making data FAIR will be clarified at various stages later in the project.

COEVOLVERS employs a digital platform for data storage and project communication and will continue discussing data management in every Steering Committee (four times a year) and all other meetings involving research activities. Data management is also discussed in the Living lab meetings and workshops where data is collected, etc. After the end of the project, project partner institutes will handle the costs related to curating and preserving their data. The DMP and Consortium Agreement (CA) outline consortium participants' access rights to data held by other consortium members and clarifies ownership of data. The DMP and CA also define responsibilities regarding the data usage during the project's lifetime and address issues related to the post-project long-term data storage (i.e. Tiimeri) and maintenance and/or destruction. Special attention will be given to complying with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

4.3. Data security

Data collected from the LLs will be stored on the servers of respective partner organisations and protected by establishing authorised user groups and users and granting user IDs and passwords only to COEVOLVERS project members. Partner organisations will take care of the backup and restoration of the data by applying their backup and restore policies.

The COEVOLVERS project will use a digital platform that prioritises data protection and has a designated data protection officer overseeing it. This platform will serve as

a hub connecting the research team, LL core team, stakeholders, and participants, establishing a digital and data ecosystem within COEVOLVERS, as well as connecting our international cousins for knowledge sharing and dissemination. It is important to note that the project website and digital platform are separate entities; while the website enables external knowledge collaboration and dissemination, the digital platform will be designed to facilitate internal collaborative actions within the project. Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person will be anonymised.

Long-term data preservation and safety will be assessed, clarified, and determined at different stages throughout the project. Published data will be retained in Zenodo for the lifetime of the repository, which is currently aligned with the host laboratory CERN, which has an experimental programme defined at least for the next 20 years. In collaboration with the National Archives of Finland, documented long-term value research data collected in Luke will be preserved permanently. For example, CSC’s Digital Preservation Service for Research Data <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/dps-for-research-data/> and the systems of the National Archives can be utilised for long-term preservation.

Partner organisations have designated the Data Protection Officers (DPO), whom researchers and stakeholders can consult with questions related to data protection if necessary. See Table 1, including the names and contact details of DPOs (Table 2).

Table 1. Nominated Data Protection Officer (DPO) per partner.

NO	Partner	DPO	Contact details
1	Luke	Heidi Krootila	heidi.krootila@luke.fi
2	University of Erfurt	Ute Winter	ute.winter@uni.erfurt.de
3	UNICA	Massimo Farina	dpo@unica.it
4	IFE SAS	Nora Hriňová	sekruel@ife.sk
5	ESSRG	György Pataki	pataki.gyorgy@essrg.hu
6	University of Tartu	Terje Mäesalu	terje.maesalu@ut.ee
7	CTFC	Gemma Sánchez	dpd@ctfc.cat
8	CETIP	Soňa Veverková	veverkova@ireas.cz
9	City of Turku	Sari Järvinen	sari.jarvinen@turku.fi

10	Magház	Gabriella Farkas	gabi.maghaz@gmail.com
11	James Hutton	Loretta Maxfield	dpo@hutton.ac.uk

5. Ethics

This DMP adheres to the following principles for processing personal data:

- Data is processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently.
- Data is collected for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not processed further in ways incompatible with those purposes. Exceptions are made for archiving, research, or statistical purposes.
- Only data that is necessary for the specified purposes is processed.
- Data is kept accurate and up-to-date. Inaccurate data is erased or rectified promptly.
- Data is kept in identifiable form only as long as necessary for processing purposes. Longer storage is permitted for public interest, research, or statistical purposes with adequate safeguards.
- Data is processed securely to prevent unauthorized access, loss, or damage.

The ethics information presented in this section has been comprehensively addressed in ethics deliverable D1.1 (Ethical guidelines for the Living Labs). [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) of the European Science Foundation (ESF) will be followed in the project.

6. Other issues

The DMP will ensure that data management and protection is compliant with EU principles and standards, and with relevant national data protection laws and institutional data management policies. Produced data will be managed according to the management guidelines and then implemented through relevant WPs.

The COEVOLVERS consortium is committed to ethical research and adheres to the principles described in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU, the European Convention on Human Rights, and its supplementary Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union in Practice, as well as in pioneering documents (incl. Nuremberg Code, Declaration of Helsinki). The consortium will carry out its activities according to standard procedures as advised by the EC. Specifically, COEVOLVERS will be subject to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, as well as ethical standards in force by its academic and practice partners. In case no ethical standards are in place, project activities will be subject to the ethical standards set by the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (TENK, www.tenk.fi/en), to which the coordinating institute Luke has committed.

Luke, the coordinator, has signed the National Declaration for open science and Research 2020-2025 in Finland, indicating its commitments to 1. endorsing the strategic goals for open science and research defined by the research community, 2. supporting and encouraging the everyday work to attain the objectives and goals of the policies and 3. actively participating in the national open science and research coordination activities. The consortium partners will be encouraged to contribute to the same commitment from their corresponding field of action.

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